

Programmable current control for 230V AC

Áron Demeter

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Abstract- During power supply repair or the initial testing of electrical devices operating on mains voltage, a current-limiting device may be required to disconnect the load if the current draw exceeds a predefined threshold. This paper presents a simple, compact, and cost-effective solution designed to protect the load from catastrophic failure and to prevent circuit breaker tripping in the event of extreme overcurrent conditions.

Index Terms- current limiting; current transformer; FreeRTOS; time division multiplexing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal is to create a device that measures current consumption and disconnects the load when a preset limit is exceeded (maximum 16A). High accuracy is not required (a resolution of at least 10mA is sufficient), but the device must disconnect the load quickly if the current draw is too high. A common alternative to current limiting is to reduce the voltage using a series-connected light bulb or an adjustable toroidal transformer (Variac), but voltage regulation alone is not sufficient. Current limiting is a safer and more effective solution. However, current limiting devices tend to be more complex, and expensive, therefore a new solution is needed that results in a portable (compact), practical, inexpensive, and relatively simple device. Dedicated current limiters are relatively uncommon among commercially available devices; in most cases, current limiting is merely a secondary function embedded within a more complex system, such as a smart plug, an energy monitor, or an industrial-grade controller. These solutions are often too general-purpose and not optimized for the specific task of current protection. They tend to be overly complex or expensive, requiring mobile apps, cloud connectivity, or advanced configuration knowledge, which makes them impractical in many real-world scenarios. Moreover, their response time is often insufficient for protecting sensitive equipment during repair or testing, and their physical design is rarely suited for portable, field-ready applications. In contrast, this custom-designed current limiter was developed specifically to address these shortcomings. It offers precise, adjustable current threshold settings with fine resolution, responds rapidly when the set limit is exceeded, and operates independently of any external software or infrastructure. Its compact, standalone design makes it highly suitable for field technicians, electronics repair, and laboratory use. By eliminating unnecessary complexity and focusing solely on the core function of fast, reliable current limiting, this device provides a practical and cost-effective alternative to both improvised protections, like series light bulbs, and to industrial-grade solutions that are often oversized for the task.

II. CURRENT SENSING

General, low-cost power consumption meters typically use some kind of energy metering integrated circuit (IC), such as the BL0937 type, which is capable of measuring in both directions and provides information on both average and real-time active power at its output. Additionally, it can indicate the RMS values of current and voltage. These circuits generate pulses with a frequency proportional to the active power. The mentioned IC, for instance, produces a 60 Hz signal at its output under a 100 W load, 30 Hz at 50 W, and 2 Hz at 10 W. For a 1 W load, the output frequency is 0.6 Hz, meaning the frequency is very low. To measure this, at least 2 pulses are required, which takes 1.6 seconds. If a power socket disconnects only after this period, the connected device may easily be damaged. The consumption meter also displays the actual power consumption only after approximately 4–5 seconds. Therefore, the outputs of the energy metering IC are not suitable as control signals for a fast-acting current-limiting power socket.

Current measurement is performed in an analog manner; in the case of power meters, voltage measurement is done using a simple voltage divider, which reduces the 230V amplitude to the range of approximately 100mV. Current measurement is carried out by measuring the voltage drop across a 1 milliohm shunt resistor, which is very small (e.g., 434 μ V under a 100W load). Therefore, a programmable gain amplifier (PGA) inside the IC boosts this signal to a level suitable for the ADC.

If this approach is used in the current limiter solution, a PGA will also be needed in front of the microcontroller's ADC, and the ADC itself must have at least 16-bit resolution. Such a setup is no longer inexpensive, but the main issue is the lack of galvanic isolation between the processor and the 230V mains line, meaning voltage spikes can damage the device. As for using an energy metering IC, measurement is simpler this way, because galvanic isolators would introduce phase shift into the signal, which would result in incorrect power factor calculations and lead to errors. However, in the current case, power factor is not needed, since the goal is not to measure power but current consumption. Therefore, it is not a problem if the measurement signal experiences phase shift due to galvanic isolation.

In addition to the shunt resistor, there are two other methods for measuring current:

- With a current transformer (CT): a toroidal coil through the center of which the power line to be measured passes. This forms the primary winding, and a current proportional to the current flowing through it can be measured on the secondary side — which is the coil itself. A voltage drop across a resistor connected in parallel with the coil can be measured safely, as the coil has no galvanic connection with the mains.

- With a Hall sensor: a broken magnetic ring, through the center of which the power line to be measured passes. The current flowing through the conductor generates a magnetic field, which is concentrated by the ring toward the Hall sensor located in the air gap. A voltage proportional to the current can be measured on the sensor.

During the experiments, an actual power meter was modified, which already had the necessary hardware and user interface.

Fig. 1. Power meter

However, since the current sensing part proved to be inaccurate, both the display and the buttons required new control logic. This imposes a limitation on the sensor, as the liquid crystal display may be damaged if polarized with 5V, thus a 3.3V power supply is required. Consequently, the sensor's signal level must also be limited to 3.3V at the ADC input. A voltage divider or a voltage level shifter could be used to match the display's signal levels, but that would require numerous circuit components.

Therefore, the sensor voltage is measured by the 10-bit ADC of a microcontroller operating at 3.3V. This means it can distinguish 1024 voltage levels between 0 and 3.3V, giving a resolution of 3.22mV. Due to space constraints, a Hall-effect current sensor would be suitable, as it is usually packaged in an IC that includes an amplifier stage. One such device is the ACS712 integrated circuit, where the 20A version has an output of 100mV/A — meaning a 2V measurement range. This results in a resolution of 1mV/10mA, which is too fine for a 10-bit ADC. Another issue is that level shifting is required, since the IC operates from a 5V supply and its output is biased at 2.5V, oscillating toward both 0V and 5V.

III. CURRENT MEASUREMENTS

The output voltage of the current sensor is a 50 Hz sinusoidal signal, whose amplitude is proportional to the current. The signal is centered around 0V, so its level oscillates between -3.3V and +3.3V. For the ADC to correctly sample the signal, the signal's baseline can be shifted to 1.65V. However, this reduces the effective measurement range to 1.65V, which is not ideal. Alternatively, the negative half-waves can be clipped or inverted using Schottky diodes. Using diodes degrades the linearity of the measurement but improves the accuracy of the samples and halves the time required for sampling. Under a 100W load, the signal measured across the 206-ohm shunt is as follows:

In the current experiment, a CT (Current Transformer) was chosen — specifically, a 20A/20mA type.

Fig. 2. Current Transformer (CT)

This means that if 20A flows through the primary winding, 20mA flows through the secondary. A resistor must be placed across the secondary such that 16mA creates a 3.3V drop across it. This corresponds roughly to 206 ohms when considering peak current. The current consumption is thus scaled between 0 and 3.3V, yielding a resolution of 2.06mV per 0.01A, which is closer to the ADC's resolution.

The CT provides full isolation from the 230V mains. If for some reason the device fails to disconnect the socket under overcurrent conditions (>16A or short-circuit), the CT saturates — the magnetic core no longer responds to further increases in the magnetic flux on the primary side, as all field vectors of the ferromagnetic material are already aligned with the magnetic field. At that point, the secondary current becomes full of harmonics and highly distorted, resulting in incorrect measurements — however, it does not damage the device.

The CT introduces a phase shift between the primary and secondary currents, which affects the power factor. This leads to measurement errors in the case of inductive or capacitive loads and compensating for this is quite complex in terms of both hardware and software. However, in this case, the goal is to measure current (not power), and not with very high accuracy, so the phase shift can be considered negligible.

Fig. 3. CT output on 100W load using Schottky diode

It is sufficient to sample for at least a quarter of a period, that is, the duration of the half-wave from zero to its peak, which is 5 ms at 50 Hz. During this time, as many samples as possible should be taken. However, dense sampling reduces accuracy, since the

ADC must operate faster. For 150 samples, if each conversion takes 13 clock cycles, 1950 clock cycles are needed. If this must be completed within 5 ms, then one clock cycle must be 2.56 μ s, meaning the sampling frequency would need to be 390 kHz.

It is advisable to configure the sampling to occur via automatic interruptions, so that other operations—such as refreshing the display or checking the buttons—can be performed in the background. Under no circumstances should the samples be stored; they must be processed immediately to minimize unnecessary operations.

Step 1: Convert the sample to a voltage value:

$$V_{ADC} = \frac{ADC \cdot 1024}{VCC} \quad (1)$$

Step 2: Calculate the root mean square (RMS) over N samples:

$$V_{TRMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N V_{ADC_i}^2} \quad (2)$$

IV. USER INTERFACE

The device from Figure 1. was used as a prototype. Using an existing power meter enclosure provided immediately available, ready-to-use housing, saving time and effort on designing and manufacturing a custom case. The original device’s display and buttons were proven reliable and well-suited for the application, ensuring a solid foundation for the prototype’s user interface.

A. LCD

The activation voltage of an LCD segment is typically between 3–5V, while deactivation is achieved with an alternating voltage of 0–1.5V, at 50 Hz or higher frequency to avoid visible flickering. The display of the power meter used in the experiment has 30 pins, which are giving access to the segment groups — specifically 26 groups and four common (COM) pins. Therefore, it operates using time division multiplex with four time divisions, meaning the COM signals are active for 1/4 of the half-period. These signals are generated by controlling general-purpose I/O pins of the microcontroller. Further details of the LCD control are not relevant to the current writing, but they played an important role in the selection of the microcontroller and constitute a significant part of the source code.

B. Buttons

The power meter’s “UP” and “DOWN” buttons can be used to set the power limit. This value is displayed on the lower part of the screen. If the measured value exceeds the indicated limit, the “OVERLOAD” indicator is activated. Both the measured and set values are integers between 1 and 1600 (displayed as 16.00 meaning 16 Amperes).

Fig. 4. Used segments from the LCD

V. CONTROL LOGIC

The processor has three basic tasks: sampling, controlling the display, and monitoring the buttons. A microcontroller with a single processor core cannot perform these tasks simultaneously, only sequentially:

```
while(1)
{
    ADC_conversion();
    LCD_Update();
    Check_buttons();
}
```

One disadvantage of this is that during sampling, the display driving is paused, which may cause the image to flicker. Another drawback is that while the display is active, no sampling occurs, meaning overcurrent cannot be detected during that time. The state of the buttons is also ignored while the display and sampling are taking place. If all of this happens fast enough, the delay is not perceptible to the human senses—the display does not flicker, the displayed value appears to be real-time, and the relay trips immediately in case of overcurrent. The speed of these tasks is more critical for relay disconnection than for the display. The relay itself requires about 15 ms to activate, during which the control signal pulled to ground magnetizes the coil’s iron core and trips the mechanical mechanism. This time must be added to the sampling period and the clock cycles during which the program converts the sample to a voltage, calculates the root mean square (RMS) value, computes the current, compares the sampled value to the threshold, and switches off the relay control I/O pin. Figure 5. shows the relay control signal (red) and the voltage drop measured across the shunt resistor (yellow) under a 3000W load. The time elapsed from the onset of the overcurrent to the disconnection of the load is 136 ms.

Fig. 5. Reaction time for overcurrent

Fig. 6. Reaction time with FreeRTOS

Unless three separate microcontrollers are used for each task, this time can only be reduced through scheduling. This is possible with FreeRTOS, an open-source real-time operating system designed for microcontrollers, which includes a kernel and a number of libraries, including one for task scheduling. It utilizes interrupt service routines (ISRs) available in microcontrollers, which can interrupt any task to execute some other code.

FreeRTOS allocates time slices to each task during which the task can run. If a task does not finish within its assigned time slice, it continues in the next one. The scheduler's role is to determine which task runs in the next time slice. Higher-priority tasks take precedence; if tasks have the same priority, they run in their respective time slices at equal frequency.

```
int main(void)
{
    init();
    vSemaphoreCreateBinary(binaries);
    xTaskCreate(ADC_conversion, (signed char*)"ADC", 80, NULL, 1, NULL);
    xTaskCreate(LCD_Update, (signed char*)"LCD", 80, NULL, 1, NULL);
    xTaskCreate(Check_buttons, (signed char*)"Button", 80, NULL, 1, NULL);
    vTaskStartScheduler();
    return 0;
}
```

The tasks each contain an infinite loop, so the main program does not need to be placed in an infinite loop. The tasks share some common variables, such as the measured value generated by the ADC and displayed on the LCD. If both functions try to use this variable simultaneously (for example, the ADC writing while the LCD is reading), incorrect data may result. This can be avoided by using semaphores, which, similar to mutexes, prevent other tasks from accessing these resources until the current task is finished. In this case, a binary semaphore (which only recognizes red or green signals) is sufficient, since there is no buffered data that would require a separate readiness signal. The reaction time of the program written this way has improved significantly: from 136 ms to 17 ms, of which 15 ms is the relay deactivation time.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The original internal circuitry was not needed because the project aimed to implement a custom measurement and control system. Reusing only the user interface components allowed focus on the development of the new measurement and control electronics.

A. Circuit diagram

The circuit is as simple as possible because everything must fit under the display. The unused pins of the display are connected to the midpoint voltage through a voltage divider, so they cannot be accidentally activated.

Fig. 7. Schematics

B. Final tests

For testing the precision, different resistive loads were connected to the output of the device.

Fig. 8. Testing different loads

For testing the overcurrent protection a 100W light dimmer was used. The result was uploaded to YouTube: [link](#)

VII. CONCLUSION

The use of typical energy metering ICs, such as the BL0937, is limited by their relatively slow response time and output signals not suitable for fast current limiting control. This necessitated the exploration of alternative sensing methods.

Among the available current measurement methods, the CT sensor was chosen for its galvanic isolation, suitable output scaling, and robustness under overcurrent conditions. Although it introduces phase shifts affecting power factor measurement, this was acceptable given the focus on current measurement rather than precise power calculation.

Implementing simultaneous sampling, display control, and button handling on a single-core microcontroller revealed timing and responsiveness limitations. This was effectively addressed by adopting a real-time operating system (FreeRTOS), which improved the system's reaction time from 136 ms to 17 ms.

The decision to reuse the display and buttons from an existing power meter significantly simplified the hardware design and shortened development time. It demonstrated that leveraging proven user interface elements can provide a reliable and cost-effective foundation for prototype development.

REFERENCES

No external sources were used in the preparation of this document.